

REVEALING THE ROLE OF GEOSS AS THE DEFAULT DIGITAL PORTAL FOR BUILDING CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION & MITIGATION APPLICATIONS

T2.1 Workshop PILOT 1 – Debrief document

Version 2.0

Date 27-July-2021

Title of Workshop: *[EIFFEL] [WP2] T2.1 focus group PILOT 1*

Workshop Time and Date: *14:30 – 16:30, 26-July-2021*

Attendance:

Attendees hidden for confidentiality purposes

Invited, not available:

1 Overall impression of the Workshop

- Since this was the very first workshop, it served as a preliminary test of the method and setup that is envisioned for the workshops. The experiences of this first workshop will be used to reflect on the method and setup of the other workshops. Based on this reflection, necessary changes will be made for the remaining workshops. These reflections are described later in this document.
- With a mere 5 participants (including OUNL participants), the attendance of this workshop was low. The WP7 project lead and other WP5 invited members could not join the workshop. Therefore, there was no WP7 input at all during this workshop. In order to ensure input from WP7, OUNL will organise a second workshop with WP7 members at the end of August. Results from both workshops will be merged.
- A number of 6 active participants – next to OUNL - seems to be sufficient for a successful workshop, divided equally among the WP5- and WP7-partners.
- The meeting took place through Microsoft Teams. A minor issue was encountered when certain participants were unable to access the chat. The reason for this appears to be the fact that these participants had been invited to the meeting, but not to the actual Teams environment. OUNL will ensure that participants do have invite and access in the future workshops in OUNL Teams environment for externals (EX_EIFFEL) [done 27/7].
- The goal of **ROUND 1** was to *co-create user stories for the applications*. The WP5 lead was invited to elaborate on users, the climate change challenge they face, the goal they aim to achieve, and the core task that needs to be fulfilled in order to achieve that goal. OUNL made notes in MURAL. Despite the absence of input from WP7, two user stories were developed. In a future workshop with WP7 partners, these stories will be revised and elaborated upon.
- The goal of **ROUND 2** was to *develop the Application Functionalities*. This round commenced with an overview of general functionalities per user. Afterwards, these functionalities were categorised as either a '*necessary functionality*' or as an '*optional functionality*'.
- In **ROUND 3**, there was the opportunity to *reflect on the stakeholder categorisation* that had already been developed before the workshop (in Grant Agreement). An additional goal here was to use these categories to agree on a *name* and *avatar* for the *Primary Application Persona* and the *Secondary Application Persona*. A discussion arose regarding the amount of personas that should be developed. The round was not finished.

2 Reflections and Lessons Learned

- Originally, 20 minutes had been planned for **ROUND 1**. This amount was exceeded, even with a low number of participants. A thorough elaboration of ‘well defined’ user stories is time-demanding. Therefore, more time should be allocated for this round in future workshops.
- In **ROUND 2**, it was originally envisioned to categorise the *necessary* and *optional* functionalities per user. Since functionalities are developed per user in the first part of **ROUND 2**, it does not appear to be necessary to make the categorisation per user in the second part. Future workshops will therefore no longer categorize the *necessary* and *optional* functionalities per user, and will instead develop a general list of *necessary functionalities* and *optional functionalities*.
- The absence of WP7 partners resulted in a clear lack of input. It is necessary to involve more stakeholders from the community of practice. It is hoped that the input from WP7 partners in future workshops will be sufficient.
- It was expressed that the expectations of participants during the various rounds of the workshop was not quite clear. This will be better communicated in future workshops. An general overview of expectations will be included in the invitation and during the introductory presentation of every workshop. Specific expectations will be provided during the actual rounds.
- The development and discussion user stories is challenging and time demanding. This will be especially challenging in workshops with more participants (compared to the first workshop). The **development of personas** as an addition to this may be too much for one workshop. It is therefore proposed to focus on the development of user stories during the workshops. The development of personas, if necessary, should be done at a later point during the project. Future workshops will therefore not include the second part of **ROUND 3** and **ROUND 4**.
- The expectations of each round will be as follows:
 - **ROUND 1: Co-creation of User Stories for Applications**
 - *Verbal Contributions* of participants with regards to telling the user stories. OUNL will make notes on MURAL. Participants will be asked to check these notes and indicate whether or not they represent the contributions.
 - **ROUND 2: Application Functionalities**
 - *Written Contributions* of participants with regards to indicating functionalities per user.
 - *Verbal Contributions* of participants with regards to the discussion on *necessary* and *optional* functionalities. OUNL will allocate the functionalities to the categories in the table, based on this discussion. Participants will be asked to check this table and to indicate whether or not it represents the discussion.
 - **ROUND 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation**

- *Verbal Contributions* of participants with regards to reflecting on the preliminary stakeholder categorisation. OUNL will make changes to the table if necessary.
- The MURAL software worked well for the most part. However, attention should be paid to participants and whether or not they are still following the facilitator. The facilitator should ‘summon’ participants before moving to the next round. The facilitator should also explain to participants that they can navigate through the rounds themselves by using the overview on the right side of the screen.
- The cells of the tables in MURAL should be bigger in order to allow for more notes to be positioned within them.
- The issue regarding access to the chat has been resolved: all participants of the workshops are now part of the Teams environment.

REVEALING THE ROLE OF GEOSS AS THE DEFAULT DIGITAL PORTAL FOR BUILDING CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION & MITIGATION APPLICATIONS

T2.1 EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 2 – Preliminary Report of Results

Version 1.1

Date 11-Aug-2021

Authors

Dissemination Level Participants of EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003518

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Invitation to review

Participants of this workshop are invited to review and provide feedback on these results. Particular points that require clarification and/or elaboration are highlighted in yellow. The feedback will be incorporated into the Draft Report (**D2.1 MS1**). The Draft Report will be subjected to further review by the Leads of WP5 and WP7. Their feedback will be incorporated into the Final Report (**D2.1 MS2**).

During the workshop, several comments were made regarding specific things that need to be considered during the review stage. Participants are therefore invited to consider the following issues during the review:

- Should an additional user story be added during this review stage?
- Is input from R. S. Lorilla and S. Sitokonstantinou (NOA) expected?
- Is input from Salomeja Rybokiene (Lead WP7 CoP) expected?

1 Introduction

This document presents the results of the **T2.1 EIFFEL Workshop for PILOT 2**, which was organised as an online event by OUNL on **2 August, 2021, 12:30-14:30PM UTC**.

The workshop is part of **T2.1: Co-design of climate change related user stories/scenarios and project user requirements (M1-M4: June 2021-September 2021)**. The goal of the workshop was to develop **user stories** and translate these into **functionalities** for the applications.

2 Workshop Setup and Process

2.1 Participants

The workshop aimed to facilitate interaction between partners from WP5 and WP7. OUNL therefore invited representatives from **IBEC** as well as from **NPA**. The lead partners of WP5 (IHE), WP7 (SYKE) and WP2 (DRAXIS) had also been invited.

Table 1 - Partners of WP5, WP7, WP2 participating in the pilot workshop. Partner noted by their GA acronym, number of participants noted (x)= x participants.

Pilot Title	Country	Workshop date	WP5	WP7	WP2	No. of participants invited (present)
Sustainable Agriculture	LT	20210802 PM	<u>IBEC</u> (1) IHE (1)	<u>NPA</u> (5)	DRAXIS (1) OUNL (2)	12 (10)

2.2 Tools

The workshop was organised through an online communication platform (**Microsoft Teams**). A visual collaboration platform (**MURAL**) was used to facilitate co-creation and record the data. The workshop was also recorded with consent of the participants.

2.3 Setup

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
 - In the second part of this round, contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL. Through a group-decision making process, consensus on functionalities are categorized as 'necessary' or 'optional'.
- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 6) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

3 Workshop Results

This section presents the results of the various Workshop rounds. The results as they were recorded in **MURAL** can be found in APPENDIX A. .

3.1 Round 1: Co-creation of User Stories for Applications

The goal of Round 1 was to develop user stories through the identification of:

1. The **User(s)** of the application.
2. The **Climate Change Challenge** that this user is dealing with.
3. The **Goal** that this user wants to achieve.
4. The **Core Task** that needs to be performed in order to tackle the climate change challenge and reach the goal.

Table 2 – Round 1 Results

User	Climate Change Challenge	Goal	Core Task
Agricultural Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity enhancement - CO₂ sequestration - Carbon sequestration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diversification - Crop rotation - Reach European greening policy goals efficiently - Because of new CAP - To monitor the effect of policy measures - To validate effects on aims 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring crop rotation; to see yearly changes in area, per parcel. - Monitoring crop diversification, to plant and declare in the same area - Monitoring Thresholds, predicting if thresholds might change are under changing per year etc. - For the whole country – national scale - Seasonal basis; one yield per crop - To boost changes in effect of policy faster
Agri-Consultants Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil carbon sequestration - Hybrid modelling: soil erosion - Soil biodiversity (secondary) - Enhancing water storage capacity (secondary) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can select farmers to enhance soil carbon - To provide farmers with enhanced spatial indicators - To provide farmers with services to support climate smart agriculture (pref. than precision agriculture) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding based on Explainable information to support the services and information to farmers - Performed at parcel level - Estimation of properties (at least yearly)
Paying Agencies Environmental Agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Area detection; burned grassland detection - To reduce the burned area - To prevent burned areas and emissions - To be able to give out fines for burned grassland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fast detection: to be able to detect areas of burned grassland immediately - To detect diversity of changing land use, bound up with new CAP - To detect bare soil

Additional comments for Round 1:

- CAP goals, working together with NOA, to be invited in Pilot 2.
- CAP is still under consultation. Question: **what is the timeline for setting thresholds?**
- In CAP, Latvia is one region.

3.2 Round 2: Application Functionalities

The goal of Round 2 was to translate the challenges, goals, and core tasks of the various users into relevant application functionalities. After the identification of the functionalities, they were categorized as *necessary* or *optional*, in accordance with their relevance and importance.

Table 3 – Results from Round 2 Part 1

User	Functionalities
Agricultural Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scale: whole country; Output: layers/numeric data; once per year for different crop type group (winter/summer grain), connected with LPIS data - Real time for some crop groups (existing data); once per year for other crop groups - Use of spatial explicit and use data for LULUCF accounting in their National GHGs inventories - For the whole country: national scale - Seasonal basis; one yield per crop
Agri-Consultants Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scale: whole country; Output: once or twice per year; uploaded to user friendly environment (to reach farmers easily) - CAP indicators in common language (farmer services) - Common legend; simple query - At parcel level - At least yearly, estimation of properties
Paying Agencies Environmental Agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators - At parcel level - Temporal scale – immediate alert when thresholds are passed

Necessary Functionalities	Optional Functionalities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scale: whole country; Output: layers/numeric data; once per year for different crop type group (winter/summer grain), connected with LPIS data - Scale: whole country; Output: once or twice per year; uploaded to user friendly environment (to reach farmers easily) - Common legend; simple query - Real time for some crop groups (existing data); once per year for other crop groups - Seasonal basis; one yield per crop - At parcel level - Use of spatial explicit and use data for LULUCF accounting in their National GHGs inventories - Ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators (to be discussed: to what extent) - Temporal scale – immediate alert when thresholds are passed - Different users, different platform application, different versions (phone, computer; layers per user groups) to be decided upon in next EIFFEL stages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If open data are used, upscaling might be possible to other EU CAP regions; but other data is restricted / publicly - Farmer user GUI. CAP indicators in common language (farmer services)

3.3 Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation

The goal of Round 3 was to reflect with all workshop participants on the Stakeholder Categorisation as defined by the pilot lead in the Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020).

Table 4 – Categorisation as defined in Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020)

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
- Paying Agencies - Agricultural Policy Makers	- Farmers - Agri-consultants - Agricultural cooperatives

Table 5 – Categorisation after reflection in Round 3

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
- Agricultural Policy Makers - Paying Agencies	- Agricultural cooperatives - Agri-consultants - Farmers - Municipalities – rural areas for declarations for payments

3.4 Final Thoughts & Feedback

- Another user story should be added during the review stage (next to burned land areas)
- Input from NOA is expected
- Input from Lead WP7 CoP is expected
- Future users of future applications could be defined better in next stage

4 Appendix A

4.1 Appendix A1: Round 1 MURAL Results

4.2 Appendix A2: Round 2 MURAL Results

<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>3 ROUND 2: Application Functionalities</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PART 1 [20 MINS] Written Contributions</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PART 2 [20 MINS] Verbal Contributions</p> </div> </div>	
User	Functionalities
<p>Agricultural policy makers</p>	<p>Use of spatial explicit and use data for LULUCF accounting in their National GHGs inventories</p>
<p>Agri-consultants</p>	<p>real time for some crop groups (existing data); once per year for other crop groups</p> <p>Scale: whole country; output: layers/numeric data; once per year for different crop type group (winter/summer) connected with LPS data.</p> <p>Scale: whole country; output: layer; once or twice per year; uploaded to user-friendly environment (to reach farmers easily)</p>
<p>Paying Agencies</p>	<p>ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators</p> <p>at least yearly estimation of properties</p>
<p>Environmental agencies</p>	<p>for the whole country - national scale</p> <p>common legend; simple query</p> <p>at parcel level</p> <p>at parcel level</p> <p>temporal scale - yearly monitoring of passing thresholds</p>
<p>This is a title...</p>	<p>ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators</p>
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Necessary Functionalities</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PART 1 [20 MINS] Written Contributions</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PART 2 [20 MINS] Verbal Contributions</p> </div> </div>	
User	Functionalities
<p>Agricultural policy makers</p>	<p>Use of spatial explicit and use data for LULUCF accounting in their National GHGs inventories</p> <p>real time for some crop groups (existing data); once per year for other crop groups</p> <p>Scale: whole country; output: layers/numeric data; once per year for different crop type group (winter/summer) connected with LPS data.</p> <p>Scale: whole country; output: layer; once or twice per year; uploaded to user-friendly environment (to reach farmers easily)</p>
<p>Agri-consultants</p>	<p>ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators</p> <p>at least yearly estimation of properties</p>
<p>Paying Agencies</p>	<p>for the whole country - national scale</p> <p>common legend; simple query</p> <p>at parcel level</p> <p>at parcel level</p> <p>temporal scale - yearly monitoring of passing thresholds</p>
<p>This is a title...</p>	<p>ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators</p>
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Optional Functionalities</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PART 1 [20 MINS] Written Contributions</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PART 2 [20 MINS] Verbal Contributions</p> </div> </div>	
User	Functionalities
<p>Agricultural policy makers</p>	<p>Use of spatial explicit and use data for LULUCF accounting in their National GHGs inventories</p> <p>real time for some crop groups (existing data); once per year for other crop groups</p> <p>Scale: whole country; output: layers/numeric data; once per year for different crop type group (winter/summer) connected with LPS data.</p> <p>Scale: whole country; output: layer; once or twice per year; uploaded to user-friendly environment (to reach farmers easily)</p>
<p>Agri-consultants</p>	<p>ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators</p> <p>at least yearly estimation of properties</p>
<p>Paying Agencies</p>	<p>for the whole country - national scale</p> <p>common legend; simple query</p> <p>at parcel level</p> <p>at parcel level</p> <p>temporal scale - yearly monitoring of passing thresholds</p>
<p>This is a title...</p>	<p>ability to use data for monitoring the achievement of indicators</p>

4.3 Appendix A3: Round 3 MURAL Results

5 Annex: Debrief Pilot 2 Workshop

Participants

12 participants (including OUNL) were invited

10 participants attended (some of whom had not initially been invited)

Attendees hidden for confidentiality purposes

Preparation

MURAL

- A visitor link to the MURAL environment was provided on the slides of the introductory presentation. Participants were able to enter the environment without any issues.

Workshop Setup

The workshop consisted of the following segments:

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.

- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
 - In the second part of this round, contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL. Through a group-decision making process, consensus on functionalities are categorized as 'necessary' or 'optional'.
- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 7) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

User stories and Functionalities

- In comparison to the previous workshop, participation during the workshop for Pilot 2 was limited. A language barrier and/or a lack of knowledge on the topic may have played a role here. Preparation for the workshop, as had been done by the participants of the workshop for Pilot 3, could potentially have prevented this issue.
- It was indicated that during the review of the results, an additional user story should be added.
- It was indicated that additional input from NOA and the WP7 lead is expected.
- It was indicated that, in the stage, future users of future applications could be defined better.

REVEALING THE ROLE OF GEOSS AS THE DEFAULT DIGITAL PORTAL FOR BUILDING CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION & MITIGATION APPLICATIONS

T2.1 EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 3 – Preliminary Report of Results

Version 1.1

Date 12-Aug-2021

Authors

Dissemination Level Participants of EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003518

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Invitation to review

Participants of this workshop are invited to review and provide feedback on these results. Particular points that require clarification and/or elaboration are highlighted in yellow. The feedback will be incorporated into the Draft Report (**D2.1 MS1**). The Draft Report will be subjected to further review by the Leads of WP5 and WP7. Their feedback will be incorporated into the Final Report (**D2.1 MS2**).

1 Introduction

This document presents the results of the **T2.1 EIFFEL Workshop for PILOT 3**, which was organised as an online event by OUNL on **2 August, 2021, 8:30 AM- 10:30 AM UTC**.

The workshop is part of **T2.1: Co-design of climate change related user stories/scenarios and project user requirements (M1-M4: June 2021-September 2021)**. The goal of the workshop was to develop **user stories** and translate these into **functionalities** for the applications.

2 Workshop preparation by PRO & APB

In preparation for the workshop, **PRO** and **APB** prepared a document in which they defined use cases and scenarios. The documents contains the following sections:

1. KPI Proposal
2. Overview of use cases
3. Users for Case 1
4. Users for Case 2
5. Users for Case 3

These sections can be found in APPENDIX A

3 Workshop Setup and Process

3.1 Participants

The workshop aimed to facilitate interaction between partners from WP5 and WP7. OUNL therefore invited representatives from **PRO** as well as from **BPA**. The lead partners of WP5 (IHE), WP7 (SYKE) and WP2 (DRAXIS) had also been invited.

Table 1 - Partners of WP5, WP7, WP2 participating in the pilot workshop. Partner noted by their GA acronym, number of participants noted (x)= x participants.

Pilot Title	Country	Workshop date	WP5	WP7	WP2	No. of participants invited (present)
Infrastructure & Transport Management	ES	20210802 AM	<u>PRO</u> (2) IHE (1)	<u>BPA</u> (2)	DRAXIS (1) OUNL (3)	11 (12)*

* Three participants from NPA were partially present during the meeting.

3.2 Tools

The workshop was organised through an online communication platform (**Microsoft Teams**). A visual collaboration platform (**MURAL**) was used to facilitate co-creation and record the data. The workshop was also recorded with consent of the participants.

3.3 Setup

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
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- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 6) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

4 Workshop Results

This section presents the results of the various Workshop rounds. The results as they were recorded in **MURAL** can be found in APPENDIX B.

4.1 Round 1: Co-creation of User Stories for Applications

The goal of Round 1 was to develop user stories through the identification of:

1. The **User(s)** of the application.
2. The **Climate Change Challenge** that this user is dealing with.
3. The **Goal** that this user wants to achieve.
4. The **Core Task** that needs to be performed in order to tackle the climate change challenge and reach the goal.

Table 2 – Round 1 Results

User	Climate Change Challenge	Goal	Core Task
(1st) - Port Authority (Environmental & Operational)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower Emissions - Pollution and accidental pollution -> connection with emissions - Thresholds exist; alert managed by port, not an accident 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emission periods - Focus is on air quality - Minimize the impact - To correlate information sensors with other sources of information - Origin of emissions (of which vessels; installation) - To validate / extrapolate to areas without sensors - Specific source of emission period - As soon as possible, action, after monitoring - Not to affect the city with emission periods - Also accidental pollution can be monitored - To predict to detect pathways to control pollution episodes (FUTURE) - Use case 3 = pathways/patterns for future regulations - Future recommendations at regional level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring - To take actions / operations to minimize impact - Port authority cannot do inspection on vessels - To make it possible to detect the origin to specific vessels - There are monitoring sensors in air q and in future water - Tool to plan the vessel actions - Within short term (2-3 hours) to organize actions (dock; delay berth) one day before arriving
(2nd) - City Councils - Administration, regional government – environmental department - Inspectors; different from port authority (navigation authority)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower emissions (overall) - Mitigation and adaptation actions in policy plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring the pollution; origin from port or from another source (industry?) - Distinction between emissions, air or water (=both) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different users take different actions - Type of biofuels/costlier? Who is following these types of fuel?

<p>(3rd)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizens - Tourist companies 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low pollution level - Being informed about pollution levels / pollution episodes / pollution patterns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To check at an open website
<p>(4th)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vessel Companies - Managers - Global Managers - If they are using the data properly 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To comply with regulations - To lower emissions - To validate if their own mitigation measures are working - Promotion of their GREEN level of the company – if they are improving - To be sure that emissions are from other sources, and not their vessels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To check if measures are working

Additional comments for Round 1:

- The excel document should be considered for this round.
- With regards to the 1st *User Story*
 - o The *user story* of the **Port Authority** concerns Use Case 1 and Use Case 3 (=future). More information can be found in the excel document that was made in preparation for this workshop.
 - o For the climate change challenge: what is measured? Only air quality or also other compartments?
- With regards to the 2nd *User Story*
 - o The city council should be asked for more detail on the specific user.
- With regards to the 4th *User Story*
 - o It is preferred to refer to ‘vessel companies’ instead of ‘shipping companies’.
 - o The specific term ‘cruise companies’ should be avoided
 - o More specific; preferably to take generic: Shipping companies

4.2 Round 2: Application Functionalities

The goal of Round 2 was to translate the challenges, goals, and core tasks of the various users into relevant application functionalities. After the identification of the functionalities, they were categorized as *necessary* or *optional*, in accordance with their relevance and importance.

Table 3 – Results from Round 2 Part 1

User	Functionalities
Port Authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor pollution and detect episodes over the TLV - Correlate in-situ data to GEOS data - Calculate the source of the possible origin of a pollution episode - Decision support - Alerts emission - Pollution episodes prediction - Historical data - Link pollution episodes to its right source - Recommendations based on the predictions - Identify any possible seasonal pollution pattern - Send alert if a high emission is predicted - Send alert if a high emission is detected - Backtracking pollution - Statistical pollution data by vessel/company - To set future dates at half-hour interval (next day more precisely than next 10 days, than next XX days)
City Councils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor pollution and detect episodes over the TLV - Link pollution episodes to its right source - Alert emission - Pollution episodes prediction - Web based, open site - Simple query, clear legend - Congruent with authority symbols and alerts, like red-yellow-green level of risk
Citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dashboard - Web based, open site - Simple query, clear legend - Congruent with authority symbols and alerts, like red-yellow-green level of risk
Vessel Companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Link pollution episodes to its right source, the specific vessel more likely - Determine the environmental impact of each vessel - Knowing the planning in advance (this may change depending on the expected impact) - LEGEND based on GREEN labelling: (international sustainability level??) - Web based, open site

Table 4 – Results from Round 2 Part 2

Necessary Functionalities	Optional Functionalities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calculate the source of the possible origin of a pollution episode - Pollution episodes prediction - Recommendations based on the predictions - Backtracking pollution - Link pollution episodes to its right source - Statistical pollution data by vessel/company - Methodology for detecting vessels with high emissions - Link pollution episodes to its right source - Monitor pollution and detect episodes over the TLV - Decision support - Historical data - Identify any possible seasonal pollution pattern - Specific user; specific access (restriction to own vessel) - Maybe more than TWO levels of access - TWO level of access – open and restricted - Determine the environmental impact of each vessel - Correlate in-situ data to GEOSS data - To correlate with extra areas (not yet known which data from GEOSS) - SDG indicators – KPI’s (grant agreement) - Alerts emission - Alerts KPI’s (see doc) - Send alert if a high emission is predicted - Send alert if a high emission is detected - Dashboard - Simple query, clear legend - Temporal resolution = half day 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Congruent with authority symbols and alerts, like red-yellow-green level of risk - Legal thresholds change each year; comply the legal limits and air quality index - Knowing the planning in advance (this may change depending on the expected impact) - LEGEND based on GREEN labelling: (international sustainability level??)

Additional comments for Round 2:

- The optional functionality of ‘*knowing the planning in advance*’ depends on the possibilities in the future.

4.3 Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation

The goal of Round 3 was to reflect with all workshop participants on the Stakeholder Categorisation as defined by the pilot lead in the Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020).

Table 5 – Categorisation as defined in Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020)

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Port authority - Cruise companies - Shipping companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - City councils - Citizens

Table 6 – Categorisation after reflection in Round 3

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Port authority (Operation managers; Environmental Managers) - City councils (Environmental council) - Association of vessel companies / CLIA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vessel companies - Citizens - Industry in port area - Port community, not represented by port authority

Additional comments for Round 3

- 'Vessel Companies' has been added as stakeholder; 'Cruise Companies' was left out as a separate stakeholder category
- Question: are vessel companies impacted by the PA decisions?

4.4 Final Thoughts & Feedback

None.

5 Appendix A

5.1 Appendix A1: KPI Proposal

KPI proposal	Description	Related SDGs
KP3.1	Alert service for average temperature deviations >1.5 °C and when anomaly GHG emissions are predicted (>=1)	13, 14
KP3.2	Methodology for detecting vessels with high GHG emissions via AI models from O2	9, 11
KP3.3	Service for vessels and cities nearby offering pollution KPIs	9, 11
KP3.4	Service for optimising vessel traffic operations from and to the port area based on spatiotemporal analysis of pollution patterns and vessel traffic configuration to reduce emissions; at least 5 scenarios	11, 13, 14

5.2 Appendix A2: Overview of use cases

n°	Title	Description	Proposal's KPIs	Operative KPIs to be obtained	Users	Geospatial area	Data needs	GEOSS data
1	Analysis of atmospheric pollution in Palma	Study of the correlation between the port activity and air quality in the city of Palma. Once a pollution episode has been detected, its origin will be analysed (city/port/other). Identify which vessels and/or berths should change their propulsion system (fuel) to reduce their impact on the city according to the necessary investment.	KP3.1 KP3.2 KP3.3 KP3.4	<p>KP1.a) emissions/city zone</p> <p>KP1.b) emissions/harbour area (ships + traffic)</p> <p>KP1.c) SO2 emissions at 2 miles from coastline</p> <p>KP1.d) SO2 emissions from vessels at berth</p> <p>KP1.e) % contribution of pollutant sources in each zone of the city</p> <p>KP1.f) emissions/person registered. Relating to KP3.b)</p>	<p>1.-Port Environmental Manager</p> <p>2.- City Environmental Manager</p> <p>3.-Port Operations Manager</p> <p>4.-Citizens (Tourists + Residents)</p> <p>5.-Environmental Manager at shipping companies</p> <p>6.- Regional Environmental Manager (GOIB)</p>	<p>Regional scale: The 5 ports and the City of Palma and nearby.</p>	<p>Wind data of the port and within the Port; PMS- Posidonia Operations data; In-situ environmental stations (25); AEMET data; SAMOA (State Ports) (3-day forecast); Traffic - City Council; Traffic intensity map (IMD). GOIB data: Industries, Thermal Power Plants; Population registered in the different areas and the influx of pedestrians (WiFi network) in the different areas of the city. (Palma), discriminating only from those pedestrians who are not residents.</p> <p>Translated with www.DeepL.com/Translator (free version)</p>	
2	Atmospheric Emissions study in The Freus	Monitoring of emissions from vessels in the Freus area (Formentera). Focus on the traffic of the line Eivissa-	<p>KP3.2</p> <p>KP3.3</p> <p>KP3.4</p>	<p>KP2.1. a) emissions/passengers (there are empty cruises/ferries, particular boats)</p>	<p>1.- Port Environmental Manager</p> <p>3.-Port Operations Manager</p>	<p>Freus area (Formentera). Line traffic Eivissa-La</p>	<p>Wind data for the port and within the port; PMS-Posidonia Operations data; On-site environmental stations (25); AEMET data; SAMOA (State Ports) (3-</p>	

3	Berths allocation optimisation	La Savina (Formentera) to detect pollution's episode.	<p>Offering advice on the assignment of berths based on the experience acquired (monitoring + prediction), both for the emissions of the vessel and the vehicles on board.</p> <p>Offering advice to the berth scheduling service on the optimum berth to affect the least number of people. In addition, it would be possible to identify which vessels and/or berths should change their propulsion system (fuel) to reduce their impact on the city depending on the investment required. Advise the berth scheduling service on the optimum berth to affect the least number of people.</p>	<p>KP3.4</p>	<p>KP1.1.a) cruise/vessel emissions/ passengers KP3. a) cruise/vessel emissions/ boarded vehicles (still unclear). Not only mitigation, but also adaptation. KP3.c) Number of cruises/vessels and/or berths exceed the pollution limit KP3.d) Cruise/vessel emissions/route path KP3.e) Prediction of pollution episodes/ prediction alerts (unclear whether this is a KPI or a result)</p>	<p>5.-Environmental Manager at shipping companies 6.- Regional Environmental Manager (GOIB)</p> <p>1.-Port Environmental Manager 3.-Port Operations Manager</p>	Savina (Formentera)	<p>day forecast). Data on the number of passengers, vehicles, lorries carried by ships and the percentage of occupation per vessel.</p> <p>Wind data for the port and within the port; PMS-Posidonia Operations data; On-site environmental stations (25); AEMET data; SAMOA (State Ports) (3-day forecast).</p>
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5.3 Appendix A3: Users for Case 1

User	Type stakeholder	I want to ...	So that..
1.-Port Environmental Manager	Primary Stakeholder	Monitor and detect pollution episodes Identify whether the possible origin of a pollution episode is in the port area (back-trajectory).	So that I can track, predict and act when limit values are prone to be reached, and react proactively and/or reactively 1) I could carry out inspections on the possible polluting actors to confirm the results and establish the corresponding actions: sanctions, promotion of corrective measures, etc. 2) I could manage or send customised alerts to trigger the relevant actions according to the established environmental protocol, if any, or define specific actions: email to responsible persons, notifications in other applications, etc.) I could identify if there are vessels and/or berths that should change their propulsion system (fuel) to reduce their impact on the city in terms of the investment required.
2.- City Environmental Manager	Secondary Stakeholder	Analyse whether it is possible to link the origin of a pollution episode to a specific vessel Monitor and detect pollution episodes Identify the external area to the Port as the origin of a pollution episode	So that I can track, predict and act when limit values are prone to be reached, and react proactively and/or reactively 1) I could carry out inspections on the possible polluting actors to confirm the results and establish the corresponding actions: sanctions, promotion of corrective measures, etc. 2) I could prioritise mitigation/adaption actions in the most densely populated places. 3) I could promote mitigation/adaption environmental policies
3.-Port Operations Manager	Primary Stakeholder	Analyse whether it is possible to link the origin of a pollution episode to a specific vessel Be informed about pollution levels	1) I could establish mitigation/ corrective measures to that vessel or to the port management. For instance: to change fuel type once the vessel is 2 miles away from the coast, to change fuel during berthing, or to decrease the maximum speed allowed inside the port. 1) I could be aware of the environmental status of the area by consulting the indices. 2) I would be able to consult updated maps of pollution levels.
4.-Citizens (Tourists + Residents)	Secondary Stakeholder	Be informed about the emissions produced by a specific vessel	1) I could promote measures to mitigate pollution 2) I could validate the effectiveness of the implemented corrective measures
5.-Environmental Manager at shipping companies	Primary Stakeholder	Monitor and detect pollution episodes	I could monitor and analyse the pollution episodes with values above the permitted values.
6.- Regional Environmental Manager (GOIB)	Secondary Stakeholder ???	Identify the external area to the Port as the origin of a pollution episode	1) I could carry out inspections on the possible polluting actors to corroborate the results and establish the corresponding actions: sanctions, promotion of corrective measures, etc. 2) I could prioritise mitigation/adaption actions in the most densely populated places. 3) I could promote mitigation/adaption environmental policies

5.4 Appendix A4: Users for Case 2

User	Type stakeholder	I want to ...	So that..
1.-Port Environmental Manager	Primary Stakeholder	Monitor and detect pollution episodes	1) I could carry out inspections on the possible polluting actors to confirm the results and establish the corresponding actions: sanctions, promotion of corrective measures, etc. 2) I could manage or send customised alerts to trigger the relevant actions according to the established environmental protocol, if any, or define specific actions: email to responsible persons, notifications in other applications, etc.)
3.-Port Operations Manager	Primary Stakeholder	Detect if there is an excess of empty vessels Detect if there are pollution patterns linked to a specific time frame (diurnal, weekly, seasonal).	I could detect areas / lines where a change in fuel type or use of an electric shuttle would be appropriate, or modify route management. I could provide recommendations to avoid saturations, thus avoiding pollution episodes
5.-Environmental Manager at shipping companies	Primary Stakeholder	Be informed about the emissions produced by a specific vessel	1) I could promote measures to mitigate pollution 2) I could validate the effectiveness of the implemented corrective measures
6.- Regional Environmental Manager (GOIB)	Secondary Stakeholder	Monitor and detect pollution episodes	I could monitor and analyse the pollution episodes with values above the permitted values. 1) I could promote environmental adoption/ mitigation policies
		Detect if there are pollution patterns linked to a specific time frame (diurnal, weekly, seasonal).	

5.5 Appendix A5: Users for Case 3

User	Type stakeholder	I want to ...	So that..
1.-Port Environmental Manager	Primary Stakeholder	Monitor and detect pollution episodes	1) I could anticipate pollution episodes with values higher than those allowed. 2) I could manage or send customised alerts to trigger the relevant actions according to the established environmental protocol, if any, or define specific actions: email to responsible persons, notifications in other applications, etc.)
3.-Port Operations Manager	Primary Stakeholder	Perform berth assignments based on the experience gained, both in terms of the vessel's emissions and the vehicles on board. Analyse whether it is possible to link the origin of a pollution episode to a specific vessel	I could have an allocation advice tool to help mitigate the pollution generated so that as few people as possible are affected. I could identify if there are vessels and/or berths that should change their propulsion system (fuel) to reduce their impact on the city in terms of the investment required.

6.2 Appendix B2: Round 2 MURAL Results

6.3 Appendix B3: Round 3 MURAL Results

7 Annex: Debrief Pilot 3 Workshop

Participants

11 participants (including OUNL) were invited

12 participants attended (some of whom had not initially been invited)

Preparation

Attendees hidden for confidentiality purposes

MICROSOFT TEAMS

- All pilot workshops are organised and take place within the **TEAMS EX_EIFFEL** platform. To prepare better for TEAMS-usage including chat functionality and (post-workshop) availability of recordings, invited participants have been added by OUNL to a special

*It is likely that these participants did not intend to contribute to the workshop, but that they were present:

- a) because they wanted to witness the workshop as a means to prepare for their own workshops,
- b) due to confusion as a result of multiple workshops being scheduled that day, combined with the issue related to Teams invitations.

TEAMS environment for EIFFEL meetings: EX_EIFFEL. A downside to this was that participants received several updates of the invitation, which was confusing / annoying.

- All pilot workshops are allocated to an ‘open’ channel on the **TEAMS EX_EIFFEL** platform. Unexpectedly, all notifications of updates for specific pilot workshops were also sent to partners and participants from other workshops. This could have been prevented if channels had been ‘closed’ for each group of pilot participants before preparing the invites. These settings could not be altered after the channels had been created.
- It is relevant to consider whom to invite for cross-pilot participation. There has been some interest for cross-pilot participation. WP2 lead Giannis and WP5 lead Andreja were both present at all workshops. Cross-pilot participation would have been more difficult if the separate Teams channels for specific Pilots had been ‘closed’ (see previous point). The question remains: is it necessary to invite WP7 lead (SYKE) and/or other WP leads to participate in all Pilot workshops?

MURAL

- The link to the MURAL environment was provided on the presentation slides, instead of through the chat. This worked well. Not everyone seems to have access to the chat functionality of the TEAMS EX_EIFFEL
- In order to guarantee that all participants have access to the MURAL environment, it is necessary to use the ‘visitor link’. Initially, a regular invitation link was given to participants, which led to some of them not being able to access the MURAL environment. This issue was resolved by sharing a visitor link.
- Initially, participants were not able to edit the MURAL environment because the link permission settings were set to ‘view only’. Changing these settings resolved the issue

Workshop Setup

The workshop consisted of the following segments:

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
 - In the second part of this round, contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL. Through a group-decision making process, consensus on functionalities are categorized as ‘necessary’ or ‘optional’.
- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 7) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

User stories and case studies

Pilot 3 consists of three case studies:

1. Analysis of atmospheric pollution in Palma: correlation between the port activity and air quality in the city of Palma.
2. Atmospheric Emissions study in The Freus (Formentera): monitoring of emissions from vessels-line to detect pollution episode.
3. Berths allocation optimization based on experience (monitoring and prediction), both for the emissions of the vessel and the vehicles on board.

The workshop appeared to primarily focus on case study 1. It is important to consider and evaluate how relevant the developed user stories are in the context of the various case studies. It is possible that the user stories in fact are relevant for all case studies. If this is not the case, the question remains whether or not it is necessary to develop separate user stories for every case study. This should also be considered for other Pilots that have multiple case studies. Especially if case studies are significantly different, it may be necessary to generate separate stories for each of them.

Functionalities & prioritisation

- When participants mention the same functionalities during the brainstorming in Round 2, the process appears inefficient because of the ‘double work’ that is being done. On the other hand, this may be an expected outcome when all participants are invited to contribute in writing. During the discussion part of Round 2, it appears useful to group these ‘double’ items together during the allocation of functionalities to the ‘necessary’ and ‘optional’ categories.
- The preparation (presented in the excel spreadsheet) done by PRODEVELOP and BPA appeared to be useful. Using an overview as such in the draft report of each Pilot workshop may be useful. Furthermore, participants of future workshops (notably: Pilot 5) could be recommended to prepare for the workshop in a similar way

REVEALING THE ROLE OF GEOSS AS THE DEFAULT DIGITAL PORTAL FOR BUILDING CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION & MITIGATION APPLICATIONS

T2.1 EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 4 – Preliminary Report of Results

Version 1.1

Date 12-Aug-2021

Authors

Dissemination Level Participants of EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 4

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003518

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Invitation to review

Participants of this workshop are invited to review and provide feedback on these results. Particular points that require clarification and/or elaboration are highlighted in yellow. The feedback will be incorporated into the Draft Report (**D2.1 MS1**). The Draft Report will be subjected to further review by the Leads of WP5 and WP7. Their feedback will be incorporated into the Final Report (**D2.1 MS2**).

During the workshop, several comments were made regarding specific things that need to be considered during the review stage. Participants are therefore invited to consider the following issues during the review:

- Does these more simplified categorisation on users fit with the more detailed user group titles as described in table 2 (first column ‘user’)? Simplified categories are: Urban Planners; Energy Providers (Infrastructure); Citizens as energy producers (Smart grid) and Air quality officials

1 Introduction

This document presents the results of the **T2.1 EIFFEL Workshop for PILOT 4**, which was organised as an online event by OUNL on **3 August, 2021, 8:30 AM - 10:30 AM UTC**.

The workshop is part of **T2.1: Co-design of climate change related user stories/scenarios and project user requirements (M1-M4: June 2021-September 2021)**. The goal of the workshop was to develop **user stories** and translate these into **functionalities** for the applications.

2 Workshop Setup and Process

2.1 Participants

The workshop aimed to facilitate interaction between partners from WP5 and WP7. OUNL therefore invited representatives from **NOA** as well as from **ATTICA**. The lead partners of WP5 (IHE), WP7 (SYKE) and WP2 (DRAXIS) had also been invited.

Table 1 - Partners of WP5, WP7, WP2 participating in the pilot workshop. Partner noted by their GA acronym, number of participants noted (x)= x participants.

Pilot Title	Country	Workshop date	WP5	WP7	WP2	No. of participants invited (present)
Infrastructure & Transport Management	GR	20210803 AM	<u>NOA</u> (4) IHE (1)	<u>ATTICA</u> (3) SYKE (1)	DRAXIS (3) OUNL (2)	18 (14)

2.2 Tools

The workshop was organised through an online communication platform (**Microsoft Teams**). A visual collaboration platform (**MURAL**) was used to facilitate co-creation and record the data. The workshop was also recorded with consent of the participants.

2.3 Setup

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
 - In the second part of this round, contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL. Through a group-decision making process, consensus on functionalities are categorized as ‘necessary’ or ‘optional’.
- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 6) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

3 Workshop Results

This section presents the results of the various Workshop rounds. The results as they were recorded in **MURAL** can be found in APPENDIX A. .

3.1 Round 1: Co-creation of User Stories for Applications

The goal of Round 1 was to develop user stories through the identification of:

1. The **User(s)** of the application.
2. The **Climate Change Challenge** that this user is dealing with.
3. The **Goal** that this user wants to achieve.
4. The **Core Task** that needs to be performed in order to tackle the climate change challenge and reach the goal.

Table 2 – Round 1 Results

User	Climate Change Challenge	Goal	Core Task
(1st) - Urban planners - Contracting depends on scale; nat – reg – urban ; different scales – different plants – coordinates objectives - Administrative authorities (i.e. prefectures, municipalities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intense phenomena like rain, flooding - Tool is more on CC mitigation, so blue-green infrastructure and connection to adaptation measures - Photovoltaic, urban mobility, air quality connected green parks - Programme exist on early warning / urban flooding system (not in EIFFEL) - Extreme weather events: heat waves, high temp. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - co-benefits of adaptation and mitigation actions, demonstrate co-benefits - air quality application is co-benefit demonstration - greening Attica by parks gives co-benefits (CC adaptation / mitigation effects) - to demonstrate how important is to combine levels from national to urban level - to demonstrate regional/urban planning to showcase to national measures - awareness, action on adaptation linked to mitigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To develop urban structures, green infrastructures, green roads, walls - Collect data for common use places / green places - Coordinate plans at different scales - Citizens will be having power in energy producing – so demonstrate scenarios, possible conflicts
(2nd) - Energy providers / distributors (i.e. PPC/PPCR, IPTO) - Financial institutions, potential - Ministry of Environment & Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decarbonising - Is it not cheaper to focus on rural and on importing energy? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - potential of the city of sust. sources, to measure/ to provide data sets and parameters on effect - To enlarge e-mobility - New dimension is the citizen as producer of energy, complicated the market operation – new market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To develop scenarios that could cover the larger need on energy by emobility - Proximity is also important to minimize transmission costs - To develop totally new concepts as smart grids - Transmission and spatial distribution had to be more efficient on small scale - To demonstrate citizens as both users and producers of (new) energy

			- To co-design the use of land for PV, competitive use (rural areas) - 2 nd level
(3 rd) - Citizens as energy providers - Citizen as user of public spaces, transport system, health			
(4 th) - Ministry of Health (Air quality – at national level) - Ministry of Environment & Energy	- Air quality change / accidents - Heat waves; mitigation co-benefit air quality	- Modernisation: fin benefit and investments CBA	- Monitoring and alerting by threshold of air quality (accidents, base level) - Scenario analysis to plan ahead (prediction); spatial and temporal - Scenario analysis / land use analysis - Spatial scale in line with nat/regional scales, target measures in locations (MAP above NUMBER)

Additional comments for Round 1:

- 40% of population of Greece is in Attica
- All cases are related to energy
- With regards to 1st User Story
 - o It should be discussed whether or not to included contracted urban planners.
 - o What to prioritise to set goals in planning?
- With regards to 2nd User Story
 - o Is proximity important for energy providers, producing directly at the place?
 - o Example of application in city of France
- With regards to 3rd User Story
 - o Is the app being public; open app might be run into?
 - o It should be studied if data are public or restricted, should limit privacy issues limit the tools
 - o Different demonstration levels, depending on the user and the privacy regulations

3.2 Round 2: Application Functionalities

The goal of Round 2 was to translate the challenges, goals, and core tasks of the various users into relevant application functionalities. After the identification of the functionalities, they were categorized as *necessary* or *optional*, in accordance with their relevance and importance.

Table 3 – Results from Round 2 Part 1

User	Functionalities
Urban Planners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support policy decision - Comparison between municipalities - Database / mapping - Scenario planning for emissions reduction - Adaptation synergies with green infra - Screening for feasibility, space usage - Decarbonisation effectiveness to meet targets - How can I optimize transportation and mobility in my region/municipality to serve the citizens while at the same time cutting down on emissions? - Use the DSA or the tools to prove that I am taking steps towards greening my region/municipality and complying with zero carbon cities - Scale? National <-> regional <-> local
Energy Providers (Infrastructure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solar energy potential information - Definition of the supply and demand equilibriums - Assessing energy savings - Support the continuous intraday energy trading - Is the energy from solar panels (at the building or neighbourhood level) adequate to cover part of the energy needed for electric cars? - Feasibility? Cost? - Create high impact examples. Buildings of high visibility. How good do they perform? - Harmonization with the new European Energy Target Model
Citizens as energy providers (Smart grid)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to understand, direct information. What is the situation at my home? - How much money I can save through the introduction of the measures - Co-benefits: health related, amenity, travel time, cost etc. - Economic benefit for energy market operations - Will my investment be of benefit for me and at which time horizon? - Simple queries, simple mapping
Air quality officials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be able to identify the impact of interventions in the 3 domains and measures to mitigate CC on air quality and exposure - Identification and analysis of top polluters and top hot-spots. How to deal with these top issues first? - Visualize emissions per sector (buildings, transport) - Identify hot spots where more interventions are needed – pursue environmental justice and confront inequities - Which measures get my area of interest within the EU/WHO AQ limits? - Multiple levels of data access and data analysis

Table 4 – Results from Round 2 Part 2

Necessary Functionalities	Optional Functionalities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be able to identify the impact of interventions in the 3 domains and measures to mitigate CC on air quality and exposure - Visualize emissions per sector (buildings, transport) - Decarbonisation effectiveness to meet targets - Multiple levels of data access and data analysis - Simple queries, simple mapping - Database / mapping - How much money I can save through the introduction of the measures - Economic benefit for energy market operations - Will my investment be of benefit for me and at which time horizon? - Assessing energy savings - Solar energy potential information - Definition of the supply and demand equilibriums - Is the energy from solar panels (at the building or neighbourhood level adequate to cover part of the energy needed for electric cars? - Create high impact examples, buildings of high visibility. How good do they perform? - Support policy decision - Comparison between municipalities - Use the DSA or the tools to prove that I am taking steps towards greening my region/municipality and complying with zero carbon cities - Scenario planning for emissions reduction - Scale? National <-> regional <-> local 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which measures get my area of interest within the EU/WHO AQ limits? - Harmonization with the new European Energy Target Model - Identification and analysis of top polluters and top hot-spots. How to deal with these top issues first? - Identify hot spots where more interventions are needed – pursue environmental justice and confront inequities - Co-benefits: health related, amenity, travel, time, cost etc. - Support the continuous intraday energy trading - Feasibility? Cost? - Screening for feasibility, space usage - Adaptation synergies with green infra - How can I optimize transportation and mobility in my region/municipality to serve the citizens while at the same time cutting down on emissions?
	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin: 10px auto; width: fit-content;"> <p>- Easy to understand, direct information. What is the situation at my home?</p> </div>

Additional comments for Round 2:

- The optional functionalities concern relevant side effects of the EIFFEL pilot

3.3 Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation

The goal of Round 3 was to reflect with all workshop participants on the Stakeholder Categorisation as defined by the pilot lead in the Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020).

Table 5 – Categorisation as defined in Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020)

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ministry of Environment & Energy - Ministry of Health - Ministry of Development & Investments - Ministry of Infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Administrative authorities (i.e. prefectures, municipalities) - Urban Planners - Industry (e.g. renewables, building construction) - Energy providers/distributors (i.e. PPC/PPCR, IPTO)

Table 6 – Categorisation after reflection in Round 3

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Administrative authorities (i.e. prefectures, municipalities) - Ministry of Environment & Energy - Urban planners - Region = partner - Energy providers / distributors (i.e. PPC/PPCR, IPTO) - Citizens (energy) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industry (e.g. renewables, building construction) - Ministry of Health - Ministry of Development and Investments
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ministry of Infrastructure </div>	

3.4 Final Thoughts & Feedback

- Building sector component = direct mitigation + adaptation measures
- Green spaces are not explicitly meant in EIFFEL pilot

4 Appendix A

4.1 Appendix A1: Round 1 MURAL Results

4.3 Appendix A3: Round 3 MURAL Results

4 ROUND 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation

PART 2 [10 MINS]

Verbal Contributions

5 Annex: Debrief Pilot 4 Workshop

Participants

18 participants (including OUNL) were invited

14 participants attended (some of whom had not initially been invited)

Attendees hidden for confidentiality purposes

Preparation

MICROSOFT TEAMS

- Given the high number of participants, the workshop started with a short introduction round where participants briefly turned on their camera and introduced themselves. This helped OUNL to get a better understanding of who the participants were, and which organisations they presented. Given that the majority of camera's are off during the workshop, as well as the fact that it is difficult to know who belongs to which organisation, this was a good decision. Future workshops should start with an introduction round.

Workshop Setup

The workshop consisted of the following segments:

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
 - In the second part of this round, contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL. Through a group-decision making process, consensus on functionalities are categorized as 'necessary' or 'optional'.
- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 6) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

User stories and case studies

Pilot 4 concerns the development of a Decision Support Application (DSA) to enable inspection of GHG mitigation scenarios, in three urban-critical sectors:

1. Building Energy Efficiency
2. Photovoltaic Penetration in Urban Environments
3. Vehicle Fleet Emissions and Intra-urban Air Quality

Several comments were made during the workshop:

- It was noted that the ATTICA region holds 40% of Greece's population
- It was highlighted that all cases are related to energy
- Co-benefit of adaptation and mitigation actions: It was indicated that the Pilot is focused on mitigation, but that adaptation could be incorporated in the user stories to a certain extend as well.

REVEALING THE ROLE OF GEOSS AS THE DEFAULT DIGITAL PORTAL FOR BUILDING CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION & MITIGATION APPLICATIONS

T2.1 EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 5 – Preliminary Report of Results

Version 1.1

Date 13-Aug-2021

Authors

Dissemination Level Participants of EIFFEL Workshop Pilot 5

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003518

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Invitation to review

Participants of this workshop are invited to review and provide feedback on these results. Particular points that require clarification and/or elaboration are highlighted in yellow. The feedback will be incorporated into the Draft Report (**D2.1 MS1**). The Draft Report will be subjected to further review by the Leads of WP5 and WP7. Their feedback will be incorporated into the Final Report (**D2.1 MS2**).

During the workshop, several comments were made regarding specific things that need to be considered during the review stage. Participants are therefore invited to consider the following issues during the review:

- Should another user story be added for the Rescue Services and/ or the Ministry of Interior?

1 Introduction

This document presents the results of the **T2.1 Eiffel Workshop for PILOT 5**, which was organised as an online event by OUNL on **13 August, 2021, 8:30 AM - 10:30 AM UTC**.

The workshop is part of **T2.1: Co-design of climate change related user stories/scenarios and project user requirements (M1-M4: June 2021-September 2021)**. The goal of the workshop was to develop **user stories** and translate these into **functionalities** for the applications.

2 Workshop Setup and Process

2.1 Participants

The workshop aimed to facilitate interaction between partners from WP5 and WP7. OUNL therefore invited representatives from **SYKE**. SYKE is also the lead partner of WP7. The lead partners of WP5 (IHE) and WP2 (DRAXIS) had also been invited.

Table 1 - Partners of WP5, WP7, WP2 participating in the pilot workshop. Partner noted by their GA acronym, number of participants noted (x)= x participants.

Pilot Title	Country	Workshop date	WP5	WP7	WP8	WP2	No. of participants invited (present)
Multi-hazard risk assessment	FI	20210813 AM	<u>SYKE</u> (4)	<u>SYKE</u> (1)	<u>SYKE</u> (1)	DRAXIS (1) OUNL (2)	12 (9)

2.2 Tools

The workshop was organised through an online communication platform (**Microsoft Teams**). A visual collaboration platform (**MURAL**) was used to facilitate co-creation and record the data. The workshop was also recorded with consent of the participants.

2.3 Setup

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
 - In the second part of this round, contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL. Through a group-decision making process, consensus on functionalities are categorized as 'necessary' or 'optional'.
- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 6) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

3 Workshop Results

This section presents the results of the various Workshop rounds. The results as they were recorded in **MURAL** can be found in APPENDIX A. .

3.1 Round 1: Co-creation of User Stories for Applications

The goal of Round 1 was to develop user stories through the identification of:

1. The **User(s)** of the application.
2. The **Climate Change Challenge** that this user is dealing with.
3. The **Goal** that this user wants to achieve.
4. The **Core Task** that needs to be performed in order to tackle the climate change challenge and reach the goal.

Table 2 – Round 1 Results

User	Climate Change Challenge	Goal	Core Task
(1st) - Water professionals at regional authority - Regional users - hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in water resources - Drought - Forest fires due to drought - Longer and hotter summers - Soils sulphating / water quality issues due to severe rain / drainage - Water resources depleted – regional problems - Water use type can be changed - irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being prepared for water problems / advance warnings - To be prepared for different water use - To model prediction by changing incentives in future 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To take CC and drought into consideration - Better prepared for drought which is a relatively new challenge in FI - To discuss with others the specific measures - Incentives for utility companies to be prepared for drought / pipe lines etc. - Drought mitigation plans by municipalities - 1 plan developed, but more to come (at most prone areas)
(2nd) - SYKE			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Warning to citizens and specific authorities - Researching and implementing in warning systems
(3rd) - Foresters - Forest centres and management companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - Longer droughts, peat fires / forest fires increasing - Pest species - Pest species more abundant in milder winters - Forest first - Increasing likelihood of forest fires - Interplay between drought and pest effects - Forest fire risk increases if forest is sick 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving the warnings for forest fires - Way of forest management: biodiversity vs economic and how CC affects these type of FM - Provide information on pest species per forest / tree type - Improved management information - To maximize forest growth, to make decision in forest management cycle - To have less economic loss 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To update their instructions taken CC into account - Pest control to enhance incl CC future - To grow forests in a CC perspective - Revising national forestry guidelines incl CC future - National guidelines is policy-wise complex

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity goals, support in interpretation in multilevel situations and projections - Interplay between forest species (spruce is not eaten by moose) - Some companies prioritize not on wood but recreation / economic 	
<p>(4th) - Ministry of agriculture and forestry</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The climate change challenges for this user story are the same as above (both forestry and hydrology), but the point of view of the user is different 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing strategies and plans on these issues - Responsible for CC adaptation plans (leading, 10y) - Adaptation workgroup, regional groups are involved (lead by Ministry) - To discuss and analyse info to be included in measures - In cooperation with regional authorities and companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinating the monitoring; instruct diff partners to use - Collaboration to regional centres (finance; yearly achievements) - CC adaptation strategy (to update) - Updating the legislation - Forecasting impact assessment

Additional comments for Round 1:

- With regards to the 2nd *User Story*
 - o The expert on pest species did not participate in the workshop.

3.2 Round 2: Application Functionalities

The goal of Round 2 was to translate the challenges, goals, and core tasks of the various users into relevant application functionalities. After the identification of the functionalities, they were categorized as *necessary* or *optional*, in accordance with their relevance and importance.

Table 3 – Results from Round 2 Part 1

User	Functionalities
- Water professionals at regional authority	- At least at a scale of the water system
- SYKE	- Provide improved information on drought risks on the vesi.fi portal - Provide improved information on multi-hazard CC risks on the climateguide.fi portal - Improved warnings with new variables, time scales etc. - Models using new information, e.g. soil moisture from satellites - To develop simple query systems for different user groups
- Foresters - Forest centres and management companies	- National scale maps of forest pest risks (e.g. seasonal forecast) - Predictions of pest species distributions? - Risk maps for drought and forest fires - If a new pest species arrives, to see directly what might be the spatial impact
- Ministry of agriculture and forestry	- National, scalable maps?

Table 4 – Results from Round 2 Part 2

Necessary Functionalities	Optional Functionalities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved warnings with new variables, time scales etc. - Provide improved information on Multi-hazard CC risks on the climateguide.fi portal (Portal Climate) - To build a link between the data of the portals - Risk maps for drought and forest fires - More on long term; what is predicted to happen - Provide improved information on drought risks on the vesi.fi portal (Portal Water) - Two months ahead is more general, not local - To be able to show how big is the risk including uncertainties - Models using new information, e.g. soil moisture from satellites - Predictions of pest species distributions? - To develop simple query systems for different user groups - To the general public - National, scalable maps? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National scale maps of forest pest risks (e.g. seasonal forecast) - If a new pest species arrives, to see directly what the spatial impact might be - Normal maps are 2 weeks ahead; forecast more in advance 2 months ahead (improved) - Not always useful to go into detail, because of data resolution (uncertainty) - Under discussion = at which governance level CC impact has to be analysed / shown

Additional comments for Round 2:

- Clarification of the EIFFEL applications
 - o The visualisation of WP3-WP5-WP7 (developed by Giannis)
 - o Information on water resources, to expand on drought, forest pest species, forest fires interplay
- Rescue services and Ministry of interior are partners
 - o Their information need is similar, but their goal is different

o Emergency strategies by CC risks

- Most functionalities are about SYKE as user. Further discussion with CoP is necessary.
- Functionalities have to be tested among users (if it works); tested 10y ago, to be improved?
- Regarding the categorisation of the functionality: *“at least at a scale of the water system”*
 - o CoP should be asked, since it is too early now
- Regarding the functionality *“improved warnings with new variables, time scales etc.”*
 - o This has to be elaborated upon with CoP
- Regarding the functionality *“Models using new information, e.g. soil moisture from satellites”*
 - o Testing of this functionality is necessary, the implementation of the functionality is optional
- Regarding the functionality *“National scale maps of forest pest risks (e.g. seasonal forecast)”*
 - o Depends on models to be developed (if they will work on forecasting; research)

3.3 Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation

The goal of Round 3 was to reflect with all workshop participants on the Stakeholder Categorisation as defined by the pilot lead in the Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020).

Table 5 – Categorisation as defined in Grant Agreement (3 Sep 2020)

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry - Forest Centres and management companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional authority for water resources governance - Rescue services

Table 6 – Categorisation after reflection in Round 3

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forest centres and management companies - Ministry of agriculture and forestry - Regional authority for water resources governance - Research organisations as SYKE, Finnish meteorological service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General public - Municipalities, depending on scale of institution - Depending on sector – planning CC at regional scale - Rescue services

Additional comments for Round 2:

- With regards to *Rescue Services*
 - Could be changed during project (depending on topic / risk)

3.4 Final Thoughts & Feedback

None (see Annex: Debrief Pilot 5 Workshop).

4 Appendix A

4.1 Appendix A1: Round 1 MURAL Results

		Forest centres and management companies	Ministry of agriculture and forestry	Regional authority for water resources governance	Rescue services
User	Climate Change Challenge	Goal	Core Task		
Water professionals at Regional authority	changes in water resources drought summer longer and hotter water resources depleted - regional problems water use type can be changed - irrigation	being prepared for water problems/advance warnings to be prepared to different water use changing incentives in future	better prepared for drought which is a rel. new challenge in FI to take CC and drought into consideration incentives for utility comp to be prepared for drought / pipe lines etc. drought mitigation plans by municipalities		
Regional users- hydrology	forest fires by drought soils sulphating/ water quality issues by severe rain / drainage		to discuss with others the specific measures warning to citizens and specific authorities implementing in warning systems researching and implementing in warning systems		
Foresters	drought longer droughts, peat fires / forest fires increasing interplay between drought and pest effects forest fires pest species forest fire risk increases if forest is sick	improve the warnings for forest fires provide information on pest species per forest / tree type to maximize forest growth, to make decision in forest management cycle to have less economic loss interplay between forest species (spruce like recreation / economic moose) multiple impacts on the forest make more insight some prohibit like recreation / economic	to update their instructions taken CC into account to grow forests in a CC perspective revising national forestry guidelines incl CC future national guidelines is policy-wise complex		
Ministry of agriculture and forestry	same, but point of view is different so both on forestry and on hydrology	responsible for CC adaptation plans (leading, 10y) adaptation workgroup, regional groups are involved (led by Min) to discuss and analyse info to be included in measures in cooperation with regional authorities and companies coordinating the monitoring, instruct diff partners to use CC adaptation strategy (to update) forecasting impact assessment	collaboration to regional centres (finance, yearly achievements)		

4.2 Appendix A2: Round 2 MURAL Results

4.3 Appendix A3: Round 3 MURAL Results

4 ROUND 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation

PART 2 [10 MINS]

Verbal Contributions

Primary Stakeholders	Secondary Stakeholders
<p>Forest centres and management companies</p> <p>Regional authority for water resources governance</p> <p>research organisations as SYKE, Finnish meteo service</p> <p>Ministry of agriculture and forestry</p>	<p>general public</p> <p>municipalities, depending on scale of institution</p> <p>depending on sector - planning CC at regional scale</p> <p>Rescue services</p> <p>could be changed during project (depending on topic/risk)</p>

5 Annex: Debrief Pilot 5 Workshop

Participants

12 participants (including OUNL) were invited

9 participants attended (some of whom had not initially been invited)

Preparation

Attendees hidden for confidentiality purposes

MICROSOFT TEAMS

- All participants were asked to introduce themselves and to indicate in which WP they were involved. This was useful, given the fact that SYKE is the sole partner for this PILOT, and is working on multiple packages.

Workshop Setup

The workshop consisted of the following segments:

- 1) Welcome and Presentation
- 2) Icebreaker
- 3) Round 1: Co-creation of User stories for Applications
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 4) Round 2: Application Functionalities
 - In the first part of this round, contributions from participants are in written form. This way of brainstorming allows everyone to contribute and for a large amount of functionalities to be proposed.
 - In the second part of this round, contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL. Through a group-decision making process, consensus on functionalities are categorized as 'necessary' or 'optional'.
- 5) Round 3: Reflection on Stakeholder Categorisation (Grant Agreement)
 - Contributions from participants are verbal, OUNL takes notes in MURAL.
- 6) Final Thoughts & Feedback based on pre-arranged points of reflection.

General Comments

- Participants indicated that they had just returned from their holidays, and that they hence felt slightly disoriented during the workshop. However, it was also expressed that this workshop provided a start for the continuation of their work.
- There was confusion surrounding the actual application, and the definition of the application was unclear. Some confusion also existed around the tools. The visualisation from the workplan (Figure 1) was presented to provide some clarification.
- Since SYKE is the sole partner for this pilot, communication between those working on the various WP's should be relatively easy. However, some confusion appeared to exist with regards to whom worked in which WP.
- Some confusion also existed surrounding the stakeholder engagement within the PILOT, and organisation responsible for this engagement.

